

MEDICINES FOR CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17325031>

Relevance: The limited range of pediatric medications and the forms in which they are produced prompted the First International Expert Conference on Essential Medicines for Children to be held in Geneva in 2006. In addition to scientists from 20 countries, representatives of international organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) participated. Since then, research has been conducted worldwide to develop specialized pediatric dosage forms, address safety issues, implement a special approach to the selection of excipients, and consider age-related medication restrictions, as well as the anatomical and physiological characteristics of children.

The objective of the study was to analyze data on pediatric dosage forms and to examine issues of classification and requirements.

Materials and methods: literary sources for the period from 2010 to 2025 were used as materials. The study used the deconstruction method and aspect analysis.

Results: According to the data provided in the literature, modern pediatric dosage forms have several classifications. Thus, by state of aggregation, dosage forms for children can be divided into three main groups: liquid (solution, drops, syrup, spray), solid (powder, granules, tablets, lyophilisate) and with an elastic-viscoplastic medium (suppositories, soft capsules, cream, gel). There is also a classification by the route of administration: enteral (oral, sublingual, rectal) and parenteral (ophthalmological, intranasal, dermatological, injection, intravaginal, etc.) (Sineva et al.; 2014, Okhotnikova V.F. et al., 2016; Molodtsova E.A. et al., 2021).

Medicines for children are subject to a number of requirements. For example, they must have an attractive appearance, positive organoleptic properties (pleasant taste and odor), and, ideally, be easily and painlessly administered. Also fundamental is the drug's effectiveness with minimal side effects. Special requirements apply to dosage forms and routes of administration, which directly depend on the patient's age and physiological characteristics. It is not recommended to use large numbers of excipients when developing a dosage form, especially for medications intended for infants. In particular, many researchers agree that ethanol is undesirable in pediatric medications. It is important to ensure the required level of microbiological purity of the medications, and for medications intended for newborns, sterility. Sources also provide requirements for packaging pediatric medications: to prevent poisoning, containers must be difficult to open for children (protective caps for vials, special bands for tablets, combination locks for packages, etc.). (Nunn T et al., 2005; Ivanovska V. Et al., 2014; Kuznetsov A.V. et al., 2011; Khanova N.I., 2009; Narkevich I.A. et al., 2016; Sineva T.D. et al., 2019; Egorova S.N., 2019; Telnova E.A. et al., 2020).

Conclusions: A literature review demonstrates that pediatric drug development has numerous unique characteristics and requires an individualized approach in each case. Therefore, research in this area is one of the most pressing challenges in modern pharmaceuticals.